

LEARNERS' PERSPECTIVES: RELEVANCE OF TEACHING VALUES EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Learners' Perspectives: Relevance of Teaching Values Education in the 21st Century

Trena Ching O. Belarmino,* Mary Cris P. Asdali, Merwan H. Jianson, Renz Jervy A. Book,
Khiemnick A. Bialen, Raponzel B. Manalo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study utilized a one-on-one interview to gather the perceptions of the students about the relevance of teaching values education in the 21st Century. With this, it delineated the key research questions the research instrument was manage to a purposively selected sample of ten (10) respondents. The study revealed that there is a relevance of teaching Values Education to 21st-century learners because it plays an important role in their life as a student as it helps them develop better personalities, behaviors, and attitudes toward other people. The following themes emerged: 1. Students' perceptions of teaching Values Education; 2. Student's perception of the relevance of teaching Values Education, the need for teaching Values Education, the Relevance of Values Education to the Students, and the relevance of studying Values Education today. Teaching Values education is very essential to the students because of the values they can learn. Values Education subject will be an important subject as a whole, not just by integrating it into other fields or subjects. Hence, the learnings in EsP subject deal with morals, behaviors, personalities, ethics, or a subject that focuses on the human being as a whole.

Keywords: *values education, student's perception, EsP subject, the relevance of values education*

Introduction

In any aspect of life, the existence of values is important because these are set of actions, morals, or behaviors that an individual acquires and make this a personal or impersonal guideline or the basis on how they will act towards someone or something. It serves as a moral compass, which is necessary for their lives.

The relevance of Values Education is to impart universal virtues to the students such as moral principles, tolerance, honesty, etc. Its goal is to develop the student's personality, behavior, ethics, and mindset to become a better person in society. It prepares an individual to be one who can contribute to the development of society and be the instrument of transmitting good values to those who lack the concept of values. In other words, the teaching of values education is an essential instrument in the development of students.

It is also one of the academic subjects that the Philippine Education System offers. Given that it is only taught twice a week compared to the other topics, it is regarded as the least significant (Dela Cruz, 2019). Therefore, there is a lack of time to shape students' values and the guidance that the teacher can provide is not enough. There is a possibility that students will be more engaged in inappropriate activities, which will cause them to have misbehavior and bad character. Any form of bad behavior that occurs in school, can cause problems for teachers, students, faculty, and the school (Delucas, 2018).

A vital part of the efficient teacher is their attitude toward teaching values. For teachers to be able to direct their actions, deal with difficulties, and influence the aspirations and performance of their pupils, their beliefs are crucial. This study will elaborate on how the students will be able to understand the essence of values education that is being taught to them based on the values teachers have.

There are no existing studies related to the relevance of values education in the 21st century. Thus, the purpose of this study is to determine the importance of imparting character education to students in the twenty-first century, to provide more specific information on why valuing education is still vital in today's society, and to explore how students might improve their conduct.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the perspectives of Junior High School Students on the teaching and relevance of Values Education in the 21st Century. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do students perceive the teaching of Values Education in the 21st Century?
2. What are the perspectives of students on the relevance of Values Education in the 21st Century?

Literature Review

Values Education

Values are specific traits that influence a person's behavior and character. Our relationships, habits, decisions, and sense of self are shaped by our values. Education's values are similar to the virtues that define a person. The necessity for the learner to succeed in a cutthroat environment and the need to have sympathy for his fellow humans are balanced through values education (Indrani, 2012). This will assist the learner in realizing, experiencing, and integrating them into their lives. This will includes lessons on morality, ethics, and character. It is also the area of educational practice that involves communicating to or developing among students moral or political ideals as well as norms, attitudes, and abilities based on such values.

The social sciences place a lot of emphasis on values and socialization the process by which attitudes and behaviors are passed down

from one generation to the next includes the transmission of values (Makarova et al., 2018). At the systemic level of the educational system, values are therefore transmitted through suitable curricular educational goals, and they play a substantial and prominent role in the development of global education policy. According to (Aydn 2011), value is a measure that is used to convey individual conduct, identify and endorse such behavior, and evaluate events and episodes.

Values have always been a part of the curriculum. It is reflected in education which aims to cultivate good citizens and is described as equipping students with personal values, beliefs, and behaviors that will influence their lives.

Relevance of Values Education

Values education's objective is to instill these ideals in students and equip them with the skills necessary to live happy, fulfilling lives. Since values education is thought to be a means of bringing about beneficial changes in pupils, it has been highlighted to occasionally incorporate value education into various levels of education and curriculum (Kumar, 2017).

Value education is something that everyone should receive. When it comes to providing children with valuable education, educational institutions are crucial even before they enter school. Value-based education lays a high emphasis on the development of one's personality in order to define one's destiny and successfully traverse difficult situations. Education in values is important since it develops students emotionally. It promotes civility, a sense of nationalism, a sense of belonging, and religious tolerance.

Education is a systematic endeavor to learn fundamental information about people. And the main goal of value education is to instill fundamental values in students in order to maintain the civilization that educates us to handle complexity and extended development. It starts at home and continues in classrooms. Everybody agrees on certain things in his or her life via a variety of channels, such as society or government. To assist everyone in enhancing the values they uphold, value education is crucial. Once everyone is aware of their own personal values, they can investigate and govern the decisions they make throughout their lives. Frequently, one must uphold the various forms of values, including social, cultural, and universal values, which are important in life values.

Methodology

Research Design

The study was making use of descriptive research design, a qualitative research method. Without making a deliberate effort to manipulate any factors, the design entails gathering data as it is currently organized to characterize a phenomenon (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Dempsey, 2018).

Respondents

The chosen respondents of this study were students from Western Mindanao State University Integrated Laboratory School (ILS). The inclusion of the study was only the Junior high school specifically the Grade 10 students who took up values education subject.

Instruments

In this research, a one-on-one interview was utilized to gather the perceptions of the students about the relevance of teaching values education in the 21st Century. This study provides the relevant questions to be answered by the respondents in able to collect important data. The researchers' prior study, knowledge, readings, books, and internet sources were used to develop this draft of the questionnaires.

Procedure

The researchers selected 10 respondents from Western Mindanao State University Integrated Laboratory School (ILS). The first step is to seek permission from the dean to conduct a one-on-one interview using questionnaires. The researcher was given informed consent to the chosen respondents, the researcher asked for a schedule when they are available for the interview, and the agreed schedule was followed. The researcher asked permission from the respondents to record the whole duration of the one-on-one interview for the purpose of data gathering. Upon gaining the consent of the respondent to record, the researchers proceeded with the interview.

Ethical Considerations

The willingness of the respondents to participate in the study was the basis of informed consent specifying their awareness of the study's purpose. The informed consent involved sufficient information and assurance that the respondents who take part in the study understood and were fully informed, and had been freely given the decision whether or not to participate. The researchers guaranteed that any formation of the respondents will remain confidential and not be revealed in all circumstances.

Results

This section covered the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings derived from information obtained from respondents through one-on-one interviews.

Table 1. *Demographic Data of the Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Favorite Subject</i>
Student 1	Female	English
Student 2	Female	English
Student 3	Female	Science
Student 4	Female	Math
Student 5	Male	Science
Student 6	Female	English
Student 7	Female	Science
Student 8	Female	English
Student 9	Female	Science
Student 10	Male	Math

The demographic information of the respondents was summarized in the table above. In terms of gender, there are two men and eight women. They differ from the favorite subject where four respondents (students 1, 2, 6, and 8) said that English was their favorite subject, while the other four respondents (students 3, 5, 7, and 9) said that Science was their favorite subject. The two remaining respondents, students 4 and 10, said that Math was their favorite subject.

Academic subjects offered by the Philippine Education System includes Filipino, English, Mathematics, Science, T.L.E., Araling Panlipunan, MAPEH, and Values Education. In line with this study, the DepEd Order No. 021 s. 2019 stated that the allotted time for the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao 11 (EsP) subject is only 120 minutes per week which is equivalent to two hours. Which is means that the EsP subject is given less important. (Dela Cruz, 2019)

Table 2: *Emergent Themes and Codes*

Superordinate Theme	Subordinate Theme	Coding
Students' perceptions of teaching Values Education	Definition of Values Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gives life lessons • Broadens the knowledge on Morals and Ethics. • Bit difficult • Develops attitude and behavior. • Teaches the importance of respect. • Eco-friendly subject
	Values Education is an interesting subject	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All the students agreed that it is an interesting subject
	Reasons why Values Education is an interesting subject	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn a lot of things • Get to interact with new people • Teaches morals and values. • Gives realizations • Increases understanding of various worldviews • Motivates students • Provides new knowledge • Decision-making skills
	Activities during EsP class	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essays/Reflection paper • Problem-Solving • Quizzes and Exams • Decision-making activities • Activities that connect to nature
Perspectives of students on the Relevance of teaching Values Education	The needs of learning values Education today	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loss of morals • Irresponsible • Gain knowledge • Teaches ethical principles • Social media influence • Dealing with others • Nature conversation • Teaches respect • Be a good example

	<p>Relevance of Values Education to Students</p> <p>Personal Values similar to what students learned in ESP Subject</p> <p>Studying Values Education is still relevant in present times.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mistakes serve as a lesson • Make things right • Take care of mental health • Be a good person • Model • Being a good person • Absence of judgment • Environmentally friendly • Decision making • Development in oneself • Values are applied • Bad personality • Irresponsible • Realizations • Proper manners • Make things right
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In the conducted research, there were typically two types of themes: the superordinate themes and the subordinate themes. The superordinate themes provided a broad overview of the research aim. They served as the guiding force behind the study, outlining the primary objectives and key areas of focus. These themes were crucial as they set the direction for the research and provided a framework within which the study operated.

In this context, the research was underpinned by the understanding that values are specific traits that influence a person's behavior and character. Our relationships, habits, decisions, and sense of self are shaped by our values. Education's values are similar to the virtues that define a person. The necessity for the learner to succeed in a cutthroat environment and the need to have sympathy for his fellow humans are balanced through values education (Indrani, 2012).

On the other hand, the subordinate themes were more specific. They delved deeper into the particulars of the research aim, outlining the specific goals that needed to be achieved. These themes often took the form of questions that guided the data collection process.

The coding process was a crucial part of the research that involved categorizing the responses of the participants. Each code represented a specific response or group of responses that were relevant to the subordinate themes. In essence, these codes contained the answers provided by the respondents.

By analyzing these codes in relation to the subordinate and superordinate themes, researchers were able to gain valuable insights, uncover patterns, and draw meaningful conclusions about their research topic. This process assisted the learners in realizing, experiencing, and integrating the values into their lives. This included lessons on morality, ethics, and character. It is also the area of educational practice that involved communicating to or developing among students moral or political ideals as well as norms, attitudes, and abilities based on such values (Deni, 2014).

Discussion

The study focuses on how teaching values education is still important in today's generation, how EsP subject is viewed by the students, how values education helps the students, and how it can change the life of an individual. The research study deals with how the EsP subject will be an important subject as a whole, not just by integrating it into other fields or subjects. Values Education plays a vital role not just in being taught inside, but also takes part in the real-life scenarios of an individual and has still its significance to be taught in the present time. Based on the answers given by the respondents, researchers concluded that the EsP subject will be an important subject as a whole, not just by integrating it into the other fields or subjects. This was concluded after translating an answer from the respondents stating, "it is a low-key important subject" meaning that EsP subjects are seen as less important compared to the other subjects being taught in the school. The responses led the researchers to conclude that values education has still significance to be taught at the present time.

Hence, values education really elevates students' potential in performing at their best in school and society, decision-making considering the consequences, and harvesting good moral or ethical behaviors. Value-based education aims at training the student to face the outer world with the right attitude and values. It is a process of overall personality development of a student. It includes character development, personality development, citizenship development, and spiritual development. Moreover, the students partially distinguish the relevance of the EsP subject that can affect or really matters in their lives as a student and as a citizen outside the school premises (Mitgukurul, 2021). Value education plays an important role in helping you make the right decisions in difficult situations by

weighing the different influencing factors. Therefore, such training can significantly improve your decision-making abilities. Value-based education emerges as the answer to the enormous moral values crisis that our society is currently experiencing. By educating kids with strong morals and values, we can help them become knowledgeable, ethical adults who know how to use their knowledge to the benefit of humanity (Mandela, 2023).

Conclusion

Teaching Values education is very helpful and essential to the students because of the values that they can harvest from it. Filipino values system is flexible enough that some values can be learned and unlearned along the process. Values that can be acquired due to the teachings and learnings from the EsP subject, the values that can be enhanced in accordance with the topics that will be discussed in the school, and the values that have been developed due to the lessons discussed in the EsP subject.

To sum it up, based on the answers gained from the respondents, values education plays a vital role not just in being taught inside, but also takes part in the real-life scenarios of an individual. Hence, the learnings in EsP subject deal with morals, behaviors, personalities, ethics, or a subject that focuses on the human being as a whole. As the world keeps on changing, and modernizing, with all of the technologies that have been inserted, values are now being challenged. EsP subjects are being seen less than other subjects such as English, Science, and Mathematics. With the gathered responses from the respondents, they considered that learning values education is still relevant as this subject can really help an individual to become a better person or even leader in the future.

In other words, values education really elevates students' potential in performing at their best in school and society, decision-making considering the consequences, and harvesting good moral or ethical behaviors. The researchers also observed how values improve the skills of the respondents based on the interview taking place. The consistency and purity of the statements given by the respondents, the idea they shared with the researchers, and the realizations they acquired after learning or enrolling in the EsP subject were shown in the data-gathering process. In conclusion, researchers found out that the opportunity of teaching values education is far more important than the other subjects.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Trena Ching O. Belarmino

Western Mindanao State University – Philippines

Mary Cris P. Asdali

Western Mindanao State University – Philippines

Merwan H. Jianson

Western Mindanao State University – Philippines

Renz Jervy A. Book

Western Mindanao State University – Philippines

Khiemnick A. Bialen

Western Mindanao State University – Philippines

Raponzel B. Manalo

Western Mindanao State University – Philippines